

Novel free-radical mediated carboalkenylation of olefins processes starting from ready available benzylketone and weinreb amide xanthate as a electrophilic radical precursors and *E*-sulfone acceptor

Shireen Mohammed and Maher Khalid

Department of Chemistry, College of Science, Zakho University, Kurdistan-Region, Iraq

Manuscript received online 02 March 2015, accepted 23 March 2015

Abstract : The addition of electrophilic precursors such as benzylketone and weinreb amide xanthate across the double bond of unactivated olefins provides access to the corresponding three-component adducts in good to the excellent yields under mild conditions.

Keywords : Multicomponent reactions (MCR), carboalkenylation processes, sulfone acceptor.

Introduction

For many years, radicals were considered too reactive to be used productively in organic synthesis. Initially considered too reactive to be of use in synthesis, to quote Chatgililoglu, most chemists have avoided radical reactions as messy, unpredictable, unpromising, and essentially mysterious¹. Radicals now play a dominant role in the development of novel methodology and have found widespread use in the synthesis of complex natural products².

A multicomponent reaction (MCR) is a process where three or more components are react or combined together in a single reaction to produce a final product containing features of all inputs and thus offers greater possibilities for molecular diversity per step with a minimum of synthetic time and effort.

A MCR is a domino process, a sequence of elementary steps according to a program in which subsequent transformations are determined by the functionalities pro-

duced in the previous step. Three multi-component reactions (3-MCR) involve the intermolecular addition of two functionalized carbon fragments across an electron-rich olefinic π -system in one pot that are commonly used in organic synthesis to create carbon-carbon bonds³⁻⁵. (3-MCR) processes rely on the matched polarity between the different partners^{6,7}. The successes of such three-component reactions depend on the matched polarity between the three partners. More recently, these reactions were defined as ADA-processes referring the intermolecular between electrophilic precursor an acceptor (**A**), an olefin a donor (**D**) and an acceptor (**A**)⁸ (Scheme 1).

Several studies of one-pot functionalization of conjugated alkenes and alkynes under mild conditions have been reported⁹⁻¹³. Fuchs *et al.* have shown addition of trifluoromethylsulfonylalkyne through carboalkenylation processes is too effective across the π -system. But this method is restricted to introduce the CF_3 group as the initial electrophilic component.

Scheme 1. Three-component carboalkenylation of olefins.

Experimental

General : Equipment, chemicals and work technique : All reactions were carried out under argon atmosphere with dry solvents under anhydrous conditions. Yields refer to chromatographically and spectroscopically (^1H NMR) homogeneous materials. Commercial reagents were used without purification. Benzene was distilled over sodium and benzophenone. DCE were distilled from CaH_2 . ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR were recorded on Bruker DPX-200 FT (^1H : 200 MHz, ^{13}C : 50.3 MHz), Bruker Advance-300 FT (^1H : 300 MHz, ^{13}C : 75.5 MHz). All NMR spectra present in this work were measured in CDCl_3 solution. All chemical shifts are given in ppm. The chemical shifts (δ) and coupling constants (J) are expressed in ppm and Hz respectively. The following abbreviations were used to explain the multiplicities : s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, q = quartet, m = multiplet, b = broad. High resolution mass spectra were recorded on a Micromass ZABSpec TOF, on a Q-ToF Applied Biosystems and on Waters Q-ToF 2 apparatus. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1710 spectrophotometer or on a Perkin-Elmer aragon 1000 FT-IR spectrophotometer.

Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) : Merck Kieselgel 60 F254 on aluminium foil from Macherey-Nagel. Detection was carried out under UV light at 254 nm and 365 nm. Column chromatography was performed with Merck silica gel 60 (70–230 mesh), (230–400 mesh ASTM) and Baker silica gel (0.063–0.200 mm) were used for flash chromatography.

General procedure for the carboalkenylation (A)¹⁴ :

To a solution of benzylketone xanthate **1** (120 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.) in dry degassed DCE (2.5 mL) were added olefin **2-11** (2 mmol, 4 eq.), *E*-bissulfone **12** (1.2 eq.) and di(tributyltin) (379 μL , 0.75 mmol, 1.5 eq.). The reaction mixture was stirred at 65 °C. Then 15 mol% of DTBHN (13 mg) were added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 1.5 h. The reaction progress was monitored by TLC and further addition of DTBHN (15 mol%) was carried out (up to 3 more times) depending on the quantity of bromide remaining. The reaction mixture was then concentrated under reduced pressure and purified by chromatography on silica gel.

(*E*)-1-Phenyl-4-(2-(phenylsulfonyl)vinyl)decan-1-one (13) : Synthesized according to general procedure (A) from benzylketone xanthate **1** (120 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), octene **2** (224 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **13** (165 mg, 83%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.46$ (PE/EtOAc 80/20); IR (ATR) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 1730, 1623, 1307, 1250, 1145, 830; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ (ppm) : 7.79 (2H, dd, J 3 and 6 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.85 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.63–7.53 (3H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.45–7.42 (1H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.37 (2H, appearant t, J 3 and 6 Hz, CH_{ar}), 6.69 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, CH), 6.12 (1H, dd, J 3 and 9 Hz, CH), 2.60 (2H, t, J 3 Hz, CH), 1.60–1.51 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.40–12.4 (10H, m, CH_2), 0.99 (appearant t, J 3 and 6 Hz, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm) : 201.3 (C=O ketone), 149.4 (CH), 140.7 (C_{ar}), 137.4 (C_{ar}), 137.2 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (C_{ar}), 132.8 (C_{ar}), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.5 (C_{ar}), 128.4 (C_{ar}), 128.1 (C_{ar}), 41.5 (C), 39.7 (C), 34.5 (C), 31.6 (C), 31.0 (C), 29.3 (C), 27.6 (C), 22.9 (C), 14.0 (C); HRMS (ESI) : $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{31}\text{O}_3\text{S}$ Calcd. 399.1986, Found 399.1985.

(*E*)-7-Chloro-1-phenyl-4-(2-(phenylsulfonyl)vinyl)heptan-1-one (14) : Synthesized according to general procedure (A) from benzylketone xanthate **1** (120 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), 5-chloro-1-pentene **3** (209 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **14** (158 mg, 81%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.45$ (PE/EtOAc 80/20); IR (ATR) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 1681, 1618, 1306, 1144; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ (ppm) : 8.00–7.19 (2H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.90–7.79 (2H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.63–7.54 (3H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.45–7.42 (1H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.37 (2H, appearant t, J 3 and 6 Hz, CH_{ar}), 6.72 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, CH), 6.12 (1H, dd, J 3 and 9 Hz, CH), 3.40 (2H, t, J 3 Hz, CH_2), 2.60 (2H, t, J 3 Hz, CH_2), 2.02–1.94 (1H, m, CH), 1.61–1.51 (4H, m, CH_2), 1.35–1.26 (2H, m, CH_2); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm) : 201.3 (C=O ketone), 149.4 (CH), 140.7 (C_{ar}), 137.4 (C_{ar}), 137.2 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (C_{ar}), 132.0 (C_{ar}), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.6 (C_{ar}), 128.4 (C_{ar}), 45.6 (C_{ar}), 41.5 (C_{ar}), 139.7 (C_{ar}), 32.9 (C), 31.0 (C), 28.7 (C); HRMS (ESI) : $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{ClO}_3\text{S}$ Calcd. 391.1134, Found 391.1132.

(E)-1-Phenyl-3-(1-(2-(phenylsulfonyl)vinyl)cyclohexyl)propan-1-one (**15**) : Synthesized according to general procedure (A) from benzylketone xanthate **1** (120 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), methylenecyclohexane **4** (192 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **15** (152 mg, 80%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.42$ (PE/EtOAc 90/10); IR (ATR) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1680, 1305, 1145; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ (ppm) : 8.00–7.94 (2H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.89–7.76 (2H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.64–7.55 (3H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.44–7.41 (1H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.36 (apparent t, *J* 6 and 3 Hz, CH_{ar}), 6.75 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, CH), 6.45 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, CH), 6.45 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, CH), 2.61 (2H, t, *J* 3 Hz, CH₂), 1.67–1.61 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.54 (apparent t, *J* 3 and 6 Hz, CH₂), 1.51–1.46 (6H, m, CH₂), 1.34–1.28 (2H, m, CH₂); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm) : 201.4 (C=O ketone), 142.5 (CH), 140.7 (C_{ar}), 137.2 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (C_{ar}), 132.8 (CH), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.6 (C_{ar}), 128.5 (C_{ar}), 128.1 (C), 125.5 (C_{ar}), 37.9 (C), 37.4 (C), 35.2 (C), 32.8 (C), 25.6 (C), 22.5 (2C); HRMS (ESI) : [M+H]⁺ C₂₃H₂₇O₃S Calcd. 383.1681, Found 383.1679.

(E)-4-Ethoxy-1-phenyl-6-(phenylsulfonyl)hex-5-en-1-one (**16**) : Synthesized according to general procedure (A) from benzylketone xanthate **1** (120 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), ethoxyethene **5** (144 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **16** (136 mg, 76%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.2$ (PE/EtOAc 80/20); IR (ATR) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1682, 1628, 1307, 1145, 1106; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ (ppm) : 7.97 (1H, d, *J* 6 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.73 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.66–7.56 (3H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.45–7.41 (1H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.35 (apparent t, *J* 6 and 3 Hz, CH_{ar}), 6.84 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, CH), 6.31 (1H, dd, *J* 3 and 9 Hz, CH), 3.88 (1H, apparent q, *J* 3 and 9 Hz, CH), 3.45 (2H, apparent q, *J* 3 and 9 Hz, CH₂), 2.47 (2H, apparent t, *J* 6 and 9 Hz, CH₂), 1.77 (1H, apparent q, *J* 6 and 3 Hz, CH), 1.70 (1H, apparent q, *J* 6 and 3 Hz, CH), 1.19 (3H, apparent t, *J* 6 and 3 Hz, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm) : 201.3 (C=O ketone), 142.6 (CH), 140.7 (C_{ar}), 137.2 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (C_{ar}), 132.8 (C_{ar}), 132.2 (CH), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.6 (C_{ar}), 128.4 (C_{ar}), 128.1 (C_{ar}), 79.2 (C), 64.5 (C), 36.2 (C), 30.7 (C), 15.5 (C); HRMS (ESI) : [M+H]⁺ C₂₀H₂₃O₄S Calcd.

359.1317, Found 359.1319.

(E)-4-(Tert-butoxy)-1-phenyl-6-(phenylsulfonyl)hex-5-en-1-one (**17**) : Synthesized according to general procedure (A) from benzylketone xanthate **1** (120 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), 2-methyl-2-(vinylloxy)propane **6** (200 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **17** (149 mg, 77%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.4$ (PE/EtOAc 80/20); IR (ATR) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1680, 1630, 1307, 1144, 1070; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ (ppm) : 7.97 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.74 (2H, d, *J* 3 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.71–7.67 (1H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.57 (2H, apparent t, *J* 6 and 3 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.45–7.41 (1H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.35 (2H, apparent t, *J* 6 and 3 Hz, CH_{ar}), 6.97 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, CH), 6.31 (1H, dd, *J* 3 and 6 Hz, CH), 3.88 (1H, apparent q, *J* 3 and 6 Hz, CH), 2.84 (2H, t, *J* 3 Hz, CH₂), 1.71 (2H, p, *J* 3 Hz, CH₂), 1.26 (9H, s, 3CH₃); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm) : 201.3 (C=O ketone), 141.7 (CH), 140.0 (C_{ar}), 137.2 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (C_{ar}), 132.8 (C_{ar}), 131.7 (CH), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.6 (C_{ar}), 128.5 (C_{ar}), 128.1 (C_{ar}), 73.8 (C), 73.3 (C), 36.2 (C), 31.8 (C), 29.1 (3C); HRMS (ESI) : [M+Na]⁺ C₂₂H₂₆O₄SNa Calcd. 409.1450, Found 409.1449.

(E)-4-(2-Oxopropoxy)-1-phenyl-6-(phenylsulfonyl)hex-5-en-1-one (**18**) : Synthesized according to general procedure (A) from benzylketone xanthate **1** (120 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), 1-(vinylloxy)propan-2-one **7** (200 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **18** (147 mg, 79%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.3$ (Toluene/EtOAc 95/5); IR (ATR) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1682, 1308, 1226, 1147; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ (ppm) : 7.93 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.77 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.63–7.51 (3H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.45–7.42 (1H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.36 (2H, apparent t, *J* 6 and 3 Hz, CH_{ar}), 6.75 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, CH), 6.31 (1H, dd, *J* 3 and 9 Hz, CH), 5.25 (1H, apparent q, *J* 3 and 6 Hz, CH), 2.68 (2H, apparent t, *J* 6 and 3 Hz, CH₂), 2.05 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.88–1.84 (2H, m, CH₂); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm) : 201.3 (C=O ketone), 170.7 (C=O ester), 142.9 (CH), 140.7 (C_{ar}), 137.2 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (C_{ar}), 132.8 (C_{ar}), 131.8 (CH), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.6 (C_{ar}), 128.5 (C_{ar}), 128.1 (C_{ar}), 73.5 (C), 36.2 (C), 29.5 (C), 21.2 (C); HRMS (ESI) :

$[M+Na]^+$ $C_{20}H_{20}O_5SNa$ Calcd. 395.0929, Found 395.0927.

(E)-4-Methoxy-4-methyl-1-phenyl-6-(phenylsulfonyl)-hex-5-en-1-one (**19**): Synthesized according to general procedure (A) from benzylketone xanthate **1** (120 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), 2-methoxyprop-1-ene **8** (144 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **19** (145 mg, 81%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.4$ (toluene/EtOAc 75/25); IR (ATR) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}): 1680, 1446, 1307, 1085, 829, 688; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 7.94 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.76 (2H, d, J 3 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.64–7.54 (3H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.44–7.41 (1H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.34 (2H, apparent t, J 6 and 3 Hz, CH_{ar}), 6.79 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, CH), 6.73 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, CH), 3.21 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.76 (2H, t, J 3 Hz, CH), 1.89 (1H, t, J 3 Hz, CH), 1.83 (1H, apparent t, J 3 and 6 Hz, CH), 1.47 (3H, s, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$, 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm): 201.3 (C=O ketone), 140.7 (CH), 137.6 (C_{ar}), 137.2 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (C_{ar}), 132.8 (CH), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.6 (C_{ar}), 128.5 (C_{ar}), 128.4 (C_{ar}), 128.1 (C_{ar}), 127.0 (C_{ar}), 80.7 (C), 49.6 (C), 35.8 (C), 35.0 (C), 25.1 (C); HRMS (ESI): $[M+H]^+$ $C_{20}H_{23}O_4S$ Calcd. 359.1317, Found 359.1319.

(E)-1-Phenyl-2-(2-(2-(phenylsulfonyl)vinyl)tetrahydro-2H-pyran-3-yl)ethanone (**20**): Synthesized according to general procedure (A) from benzylketone xanthate **1** (120 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), 3,4-dihydro-2H-pyran **9** (168 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **20** (137 mg, 74%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.35$ (PE/EtOAc 75/25); IR (ATR) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}): 1681, 1447, 1306, 1182, 1082, 719, 687; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 7.99 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.83 (2H, d, J 3 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.65–7.56 (3H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.44–7.29 (3H, m, CH_{ar}), 6.43 (1H, dd, J 6 and 9 Hz, CH), 6.33 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, CH_{ar}), 4.18 (1H, dd, J 6 and 3 Hz, CH), 3.78–3.64 (2H, m, CH), 2.65 (1H, dd, J 6 and 9 Hz, CH), 2.42 (1H, dd, J 6 and 9 Hz, CH), 2.20–1.95 (1H, m, CH), 1.83–1.69 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.44–1.38 (1H, m, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$, 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm): 201.3 (C=O ketone), 140.7 (CH), 138.2 (C_{ar}), 136.9 (C_{ar}), 135.9 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (C_{ar}), 132.7 (CH), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.6 (C_{ar}), 128.4 (C_{ar}), 73.2 (C), 67.5 (C), 44.6 (C), 39.5 (C), 26.2 (C),

24.7 (C); HRMS (ESI): $[M+H]^+$ $C_{21}H_{23}O_4S$ Calcd. 371.1317, Found 371.1318.

(E)-Tert-butyl-3-(2-oxo-2-phenylethyl)-2-(2-(phenylsulfonyl)vinyl)piperidine-1-carboxylate (**21**): Synthesized according to general procedure (A) from benzylketone xanthate **1** (120 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), tert-butyl 3,4-dihydropyridine-1(2H)-carboxylate **10** (168 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **21** (171 mg, 73%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.33$ (PE/EtOAc 70/30); IR (ATR) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}): 1681, 1408, 1318, 1308, 1163, 1085, 732; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 7.94–7.89 (2H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.79 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.57–7.51 (3H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.47–7.44 (1H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.37 (2H, apparent t, J 6 and 3 Hz, CH_{ar}), 6.54 (1H, d, J 6 Hz, CH), 6.34 (1H, dd, J 3 and 6 Hz, CH), 3.97 (1H, dd, J 6 and 9 Hz, CH), 3.90–3.81 (1H, m, CH), 2.65 (1H, dd, J 3 and 6 Hz, CH), 2.44 (1H, dd, J 3 and 9 Hz, CH), 2.24–2.18 (1H, m, CH), –1.96 (1H, m, CH), 1.90–1.73 (1H, m, CH), 1.44 (9H, s, $3CH_3$); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$, 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm): 201.5 (C=O ketone), 153.3 (C=O ester), 136.9 (CH), 135.8 (C_{ar}), 134.1 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (C_{ar}), 132.0 (C_{ar}), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.6 (C_{ar}), 128.4 (C_{ar}), 128.1 (C_{ar}), 81.0 (C), 51.1 (C), 47.0 (C), 42.9 (C), 40.8 (C), 28.4 (C), 27.1 (C), 23.3 (C); HRMS (ESI): $[M+H]^+$ $C_{26}H_{32}NO_5S$ Calcd. 470.2001, Found 470.2000.

*General procedure for the carbo-alkenylation (B)*¹⁴:

To a solution of *O*-ethyl *S*-(2-(methoxy(methyl)amino)-2-oxoethyl)carbonodithioate **22** (112 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.) in dry degassed DCE (2.5 mL) were added olefin **2-11** (2 mmol, 4 eq.), *E*-bissulfone **12** (1.2 eq.) and di(tributyltin) (3793 μ L, 0.75 mmol, 1.5 eq.). The reaction mixture was stirred at 65 °C. Then 15 mol% of DTBHN (13 mg) were added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 1.5 h. The reaction progress was monitored by TLC and further addition of DTBHN (15 mol%) was carried out (up to 3 more times) depending on the quantity of bromide remaining. The reaction mixture was then concentrated under reduced pressure and purified by chromatography on silica gel.

(E)-*N*-Methoxy-*N*-methyl-4-(2-(phenylsulfonyl)vinyl)-decanamide (**23**): Synthesized according to general procedure (B) from *O*-ethyl *S*-(2-(methoxy(methyl)amino)-

2-oxoethyl)carbonodithioate **22** (112 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), octene **2** (224 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **23** (162 mg, 85%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.35$ (PE/EtOAc 60/40); IR (ATR) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1659, 1307, 1250, 830; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ (ppm) : 7.89–7.90 (2H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.63–7.56 (3H, m, CH_{ar}), 6.65 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, CH_{ar}), 6.12 (1H, dd, *J* 3 and 9 Hz, CH), 3.86 (3H, s, CH), 3.20 (3H, s, CH), 2.23 (2H, t, *J* 3 Hz, CH₂), 2.02–1.94 (1H, m, CH), 1.63 (1H, appearant q, *J* 3 and 9 Hz, CH), 1.56 (1H, appearant q, *J* 3 and 9 Hz, CH), 1.41–1.23 (10H, m, CH₂), 0.98 (3H, appearant t, *J* 6 and 3 Hz, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm) : 171.7 (C=O amide), 140.7 (C_{ar}), 137.4 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (CH), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.1 (C_{ar}), 57.6 (C_{ar}), 41.5 (C), 34.5 (C), 33.0 (C), 32.4 (C), 31.6 (C), 29.0 (C), 27.6 (C), 14.0 (C); HRMS (ESI) : [M+H]⁺ C₂₀H₃₂NO₄S Calcd. 382.2052, Found 382.2050.

(E)-7-Chloro-*N*-methoxy-*N*-methyl-4-(2-(phenylsulfonyl)vinyl)heptanamide (**24**) : Synthesized according to general procedure (**B**) from *O*-ethyl *S*-(2-(methoxy(methyl)amino)-2-oxoethyl)carbonodithioate **22** (112 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), 5-chloro-1-pentene **3** (209 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **24** (157 mg, 84%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.3$ (PE/EtOAc 70/30); IR (ATR) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1659, 1307, 1144; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ (ppm) : 6.90 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.63–7.51 (3H, m, CH_{ar}), 6.67 (1H, d, *J* 12 Hz, CH), 6.12 (1H, dd, *J* 3 and 9 Hz, CH), 3.89 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.37 (2H, appearant t, *J* 6 and 3 Hz, CH₂), 3.25 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.28 (2H, t, *J* 3 Hz, CH₂), 2.02–1.94 (1H, m, CH), 1.65–1.53 (4H, m, CH₂), 1.34–1.25 (2H, m, CH₂); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm) : 171.1 (C=O amide), 149.4 (CH), 140.7 (C_{ar}), 137.4 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (CH), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.1 (C_{ar}), 57.6 (C), 45.6 (C), 41.5 (C), 33.0 (C), 32.9 (C), 32.4 (C), 32.1 (C), 28.7 (C); HRMS (ESI) : [M+Na]⁺ C₁₇H₂₄ClNO₄SNa Calcd. 396.1048, Found 396.1049.

(E)-*N*-Methoxy-*N*-methyl-3-(1-(2-(phenylsulfonyl)vinyl)cyclohexyl)propanamide (**25**) : Synthesized according to general procedure (**B**) from *O*-ethyl *S*-(2-

(methoxy(methyl)amino)-2-oxoethyl)carbonodithioate **22** (112 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), methylenecyclohexane **4** (192 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **25** (152 mg, 81%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.34$ (PE/EtOAc 70/30); IR (ATR) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1659, 1445, 1306, 1082, 735, 683; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ (ppm) : 7.95 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.64–7.52 (3H, m, CH_{ar}), 6.65 (1H, d, *J* 12 Hz, CH), 6.45 (1H, d, *J* 12 Hz, CH), 3.91 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.27 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.34 (2H, appearant t, *J* 3 and 6 Hz, CH₂), 1.73–1.61 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.58–1.41 (8H, m, CH₂), 1.39–1.30 (2H, m, CH₂); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm) : 172.2 (C=O amide), 142.5 (CH), 140.7 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (CH), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.1 (C_{ar}), 125.5 (C_{ar}), 57.6 (C), 37.4 (C), 35.2 (C), 32.1 (C), 32.0 (C), 25.6 (C), 25.5 (C); HRMS (ESI) : [M+H]⁺ C₁₉H₂₈NO₄SNa Calcd. 366.1739, Found 366.1740.

(E)-4-Ethoxy-*N*-methoxy-*N*-methyl-6-(phenylsulfonyl)hex-5-enamide (**26**) : Synthesized according to general procedure (**B**) from *O*-ethyl *S*-(2-(methoxy(methyl)amino)-2-oxoethyl)carbonodithioate **22** (112 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), ethoxyethene **4** (144 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **26** (152 mg, 80%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.22$ (PE/EtOAc 90/10); IR (ATR) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1658, 1599, 1049; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ (ppm) : 8.10 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.72–7.68 (1H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.60 (2H, appearant t, *J* 6 and 3 Hz, CH_{ar}), 6.67 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, CH), 6.31 (1H, dd, *J* 3 and 9 Hz, CH), 3.87 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.44 (2H, q, *J* 3 Hz, CH₂), 3.27 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.34 (2H, appearant t, *J* 6 and 3 Hz, CH₂), 1.81–1.75 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.15 (3H, appearant t, *J* 6 and 3 Hz, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm) : 201.3 (C=O amide), 142.6 (CH), 140.7 (C_{ar}), 137.2 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (C_{ar}), 132.8 (C_{ar}), 132.2 (C_{ar}), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.6 (C_{ar}), 128.4 (C_{ar}), 128.1 (C_{ar}), 79.2 (C), 64.5 (C), 36.2 (C), 30.7 (C), 15.5 (C); HRMS (ESI) : [M+H]⁺ C₁₆H₂₄NO₅S Calcd. 342.1375, Found 342.1376.

(E)-4-(*Tert*-butoxy)-*N*-methoxy-*N*-methyl-6-(phenylsulfonyl)hex-5-enamide (**27**) : Synthesized according to general procedure (**B**) from *O*-ethyl *S*-(2-(methoxy-

(methyl)amino)-2-oxoethyl)carbonodithioate **22** (112 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), 2-methyl-2-(vinylloxy)propane **6** (200 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **27** (144 mg, 78%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.37$ (PE/EtOAc 80/20); IR (ATR) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 1658, 1630, 1307, 1070; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 8.10 (2H, d, *J* 3 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.72–7.68 (1H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.60 (2H, apparent t, *J* 9 Hz, CH_{ar}), 6.74 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, CH_{ar}), 6.31 (1H, dd, *J* 3 and 9 Hz, CH_{ar}), 3.90–3.87 (1H, m, CH), 3.86 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.27 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.33 (2H, t, *J* 3 Hz, CH₂), 1.82–1.76 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.23 (9H, s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm): 171.7 (C=O amide), 141.7 (CH), 140.7 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (CH), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.1 (C_{ar}), 73.8 (C), 73.3 (C), 57.6 (C), 32.4 (C), 32.3 (C), 31.8 (C), 29.1 (C); HRMS (ESI): [M+H]⁺ C₁₈H₂₈NO₅S Calcd. 370.1688, Found 370.1686.

(E)-6-(Methoxy(methyl)amino)-6-oxo-1-(phenylsulfonyl)hex-1-en-3-yl acetate (**28**): Synthesized according to general procedure (**B**) from *O*-ethyl *S*-(2-(methoxy(methyl)amino)-2-oxoethyl)carbonodithioate **22** (112 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), 1-(vinylloxy)propan-2-one **7** (200 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **28** (135 mg, 76%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.35$ (toluene/EtOAc 90/10); IR (ATR) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 1652, 1308, 1226, 1147; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 7.99–7.91 (2H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.63–7.54 (3H, m, CH_{ar}), 6.75 (1H, d, *J* 6 Hz, CH), 5.25 (1H, apparent q, *J* 3 and 6 Hz, CH), 3.87 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.16 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.27 (2H, t, *J* 3 Hz, CH), 2.04 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.90–1.83 (2H, m, CH₂); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm): 171.7 (C=O amide), 170.7 (C=O ester), 142.9 (CH), 140.7 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (C_{ar}), 131.8 (CH), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.1 (C_{ar}), 73.5 (C), 57.6 (C), 32.4 (C), 31.8 (C), 30.3 (C), 21.2 (C); HRMS (ESI): [M+H]⁺ C₁₆H₂₂NO₆S Calcd. 356.1168, Found 356.1166.

(E)-*N*,4-Dimethoxy-*N*,4-dimethyl-6-(phenylsulfonyl)hex-5-enamide (**29**): Synthesized according to general procedure (**B**) from *O*-ethyl *S*-(2-(methoxy(methyl)amino)-2-oxoethyl)carbonodithioate **22** (112 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), 2-methoxyprop-1-ene **8** (144 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.)

and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **29** (139 mg, 79%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.43$ (PE/EtOAc 80/20); IR (ATR) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 1651, 1447, 1307, 1085, 830, 753, 688; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 8.00–7.91 (2H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.65–7.53 (3H, m, CH_{ar}), 6.79 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, CH), 6.63 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, CH), 3.85 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.27 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.25 (3H, s, CH), 2.08–2.22 (3H, m, CH and CH₂), 1.83 (1H, t, *J* 3 Hz, CH), 1.33 (3H, s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm): 172.2 (C=O amide), 140.7 (CH), 137.6 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (CH), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.1 (C_{ar}), 127.0 (C_{ar}), 80.7 (C), 57.6 (C), 49.6 (C), 34.3 (C), 32.4 (C), 31.6 (C), 25.1 (C); HRMS (ESI): [M+H]⁺ C₁₆H₂₄NO₅S Calcd. 342.1375, Found 342.1379.

(E)-*N*-Methoxy-*N*-methyl-2-(2-(2-(phenylsulfonyl)vinyl)tetrahydro-2*H*-pyran-3-yl)acetamide (**30**): Synthesized according to general procedure (**B**) from *O*-ethyl *S*-(2-(methoxy(methyl)amino)-2-oxoethyl)carbonodithioate **22** (112 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), 3,4-dihydro-2*H*-pyran **9** (168 mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **30** (140 mg, 79%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.4$ (PE/EtOAc 70/30); IR (ATR) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 1652, 1447, 1308, 1149, 1085, 688; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 7.92 (2H, d, *J* 3 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.69–7.66 (1H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.55 (2H, apparent t, *J* 3 and 6 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.04 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, CH), 6.45 (1H, dd, *J* 3 and 6 Hz, CH), 4.20–4.16 (1H, m, CH), 3.87 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.79–3.65 (2H, m, CH₂), 3.27 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.29–2.11 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.97–1.72 (4H, m, CH₂), 1.48–1.42 (1H, m, CH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm): 171.0 (C=O amide), 140.7 (CH), 138.2 (C_{ar}), 135.9 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (CH), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.1 (C_{ar}), 73.2 (C), 67.5 (C), 57.6 (C), 40.6 (C), 32.4 (C), 26.2 (C), 24.7 (C); HRMS (ESI): [M+H]⁺ C₁₇H₂₄NO₃S Calcd. 354.1375, Found 354.1377.

(E)-*Tert*-butyl-3-(2-(methoxy(methyl)amino)-2-oxoethyl)-2-(2-(phenylsulfonyl)vinyl)piperidine-1-carboxylate (**31**): Synthesized according to general procedure (**B**) from *O*-ethyl *S*-(2-(methoxy(methyl)amino)-2-oxoethyl)carbonodithioate **22** (112 mg, 0.5 mmol, 1 eq.), *tert*-butyl 3,4-dihydropyridine-1(2*H*)-carboxylate **10** (168

mg, 2 mmol, 4 eq.) and *E*-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene **12** (185 mg, 0.6 mmol, 1.2 eq.) in 1,2-DCE. Purification by flash chromatography (silica gel, 80/20 PE/EtOAc) afforded **31** (169 mg, 75%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.35$ (PE/EtOAc 72/28); IR (ATR) ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 1652, 1410, 1320, 1160, 1085, 750; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 7.93 (2H, d, J 3 Hz, CH_{ar}), 7.65–7.57 (3H, m, CH_{ar}), 7.01 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, CH_{ar}), 6.36 (1H, dd, J 6 and 9 Hz, CH), 3.99–3.95 (1H, m, CH), 3.91 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.89–3.84 (1H, m, CH), 3.47–3.42 (1H, m, CH), 3.26 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.04–1.76 (6H, m, CH_2), 1.39 (9H, s, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75.5 MHz) δ (ppm): 171.01 (C=O amide), 153.3 (C=O ester), 140.7 (CH), 135.8 (C_{ar}), 134.1 (C_{ar}), 133.0 (CH), 129.1 (C_{ar}), 128.1 (C_{ar}), 81.0 (C), 57.6 (C), 42.9 (C), 40.6 (C), 39.2 (C), 32.4 (C), 28.4 (C), 27.1 (C), 23.3 (C); HRMS (ESI): $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}$ Calcd. 453.2059, Found 453.2061.

Results and discussion

Based on ADA-processes concept¹⁵, we described here the development of a new free-radical carboalkenylation

of electron rich olefins¹⁶. The strategy of this reaction starts with generation of tin radical chain from the addition of DTBHN as an initiator. Tin radical can abstract the xanthate group from benzylketone or amide substrates (**A**) consequently and produce an electrophilic radical (**Ai**). Addition of the latter onto olefins (**D**) produced the nucleophilic radical (**Di**) which was finally trapped by electron-poor *E*-vinylbisphenylsulfone acceptor (**A**), affording the desired products (**P**) and releasing the PhSO_2 radical through β -fragmentation process to propagate the radical chain (Scheme 2). (For reactions using sulfone acceptors under radical conditions, see Reference¹⁷).

Preliminary experiments were carried out using benzylketone xanthate **1**, as an electrophilic radical precursor, oct-1-ene **2** and alkenylsulfone **12** as a final acceptor. When 1.5 equiv. of $(\text{Bu}_3\text{Sn})_2$ and 0.15 equiv. of di-tert-butyl hyponitrite (DTBHN) were used to initiate the process in refluxing DCE as a solvent (Scheme 3, Table 1). We were pleased to find that the carboalkenylation product **13** was obtained in very good yield (entry 1). A similar behavior was observed with olefins **3** and **4**

Scheme 2. The mechanism of three-component free-radical carboalkenylation processes.

Scheme 3. Synthesis of carboalkenylation (**A**).

Table 1. Three-component carboalkenylation of various olefins using benzylketone xanthate

Entry	Olefin substrate	Olefin structure	Product	Yield (%)
1	2		83	
2	3		81	
3	4		80	
4	5		76	
5	6		77	
6	7		79	
7	8		81	
8	9		74	
9	10		73	

(entry 2 and 3). The study was then extended to vinyl- and allylethers **5** and **6** leading respectively to **16** and **17** in good yields (entry 4 and 5). Also vinyl acetate **7** led to the expected product **18** in a good yield (entry 6). Using olefin **8**, compound **19** bearing a quaternary center was isolated in very good yield (entry 7). The process was also tested with electron rich olefins such as dihydropyran **9** and dihydro-pyridine **10** which produced the desired products **20** and **21** respectively in satisfying yields

(entry 8 and 9).

We then extended the three-component process to the analogous carboalkenylation using Weinreb amide xanthate **22** as another electrophilic radical precursor in multi-component reactions (Scheme 4, Table 2). Pleasingly, the desired products **23** and **24** were obtained respectively in a very good yield (entry 1 and 2). The amide substrate **22** was also shown to react efficiently with methylene cyclohexene **4** (entry 3). The high reactivity of

Table 2. Three-component carboalkenylation of various olefins using Weinreb amide xanthate

Entry	Olefin substrate	Olefin structure	Product	Yield (%)
1	2			85
2	3			84
3	4			81
4	5			80
5	6			77
6	7			78
7	8			76
8	9			79
9	10			75

12 was then altered by introducing a vinyl- and allylethers **5** and **6** onto the alkene (entry 4 and 5). This reaction was also examined with olefin **7** leading to **28** with high yield (entry 6). Generation of product **29** with quaternary center carbon was also obtained with a good yield (entry 7). The process was also compatible with electron-rich olefins such as 3,4-dihydro-2*H*-pyran **9** and N-Boc-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-pyridine **10** which produced the expected products **30** and **31** in a good yields (entry 8 and 9).

Conclusion

In summary, we reported here novel free-radical mediate carboalkenylation processes, starting from readily available benzylketone and Weinreb amide xanthate, different olefins and *E*-sulfone acceptor. This three-component reaction proceed through the addition of a radical species derived from a xanthate and a vinylsulfone across the olefinic groups backbone and formation of two new carbon-carbon bonds, leading to valuable intermediates for useful application in organic synthesis, such as preparation of polysubstituted cyclic building blocks.

Acknowledgement

We gratefully acknowledge (Bordeaux 1) University (France), the Kurdistan Government and the HCDP Program for financial support.

References

1. C. Chatgialoglu, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1992, **25**, 188.
2. D. K. Barton and S. W. McCombie, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1975, 1574.
3. I. Ryu and N. Sonoda, *Angew. Chem.*, 1996, **35**, 1050.
4. I. Ryu, H. Muraoka, N. Kambe, M. Komatsu and N. Sonoda, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1996, **61**, 6396.
5. E. Godineau and Y. Landais, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **129**, 12662.
6. F. DeVleeschouwer, V. VanSpeybroeck, M. Waroquier, P. Geerlings and F. DeProft, *Org. Lett.*, 2007, **9**, 2721.
7. N. L. Arthur, "Organic Synthesis Formation of Carbon-Carbon Bonds", Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1986, Chap. 2, pp. 4-35.
8. E. Godineau and Y. Landais, *Chem.-Eur. J.*, 2009, **15**, 3044.
9. B. Quiclet-Sire and S. Z. Zard, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 1996, **118**, 1209.
10. K. Miura, N. Fujisawa, H. Saito, D. Wang and A. Hosomi, *Org. Lett.*, 2001, **3**, 2591.
11. N. A. Porter, B. Giese and D. P. Curran, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1991, **24**, 296.
12. M. P. Sibi and N. A. Porter, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1999, **32**, 163.
13. A. P. Schaffner, K. Sarkum and P. Renaud, *Hel. Chim. Acta*, 2006, **89**, 2450.
14. V. Liautard, F. Robert and Y. Landais, *Org. Lett.*, 2011, **13**, 2658.
15. E. Godineau and Y. Landais, *Chem.-Eur. J.*, 2009, **15**, 3044.
16. A. Gozdz and P. Maslak, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1991, **56**, 2179.
17. (a) I. Ryu, H. Kuriyama, S. Minakata, M. Komatsu, J.-Y. Yoon and S. Kim, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **121**, 12190; (b) S. Kim and S. Kim, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 2007, **80**, 809; (c) S. Kim, H.-J. Song, T. L. Choi and J.-Y. Yoon, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2001, **40**, 2524; (d) S. Kim and J.-Y. Yoon, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **119**, 5982; (e) F. Bertrand, F. Le Guyader, L. Liguori, G. Ouvry, B. Quiclet-Sire, S. Seguin and S. Z. Zard, *C. R. Acad. Sci.*, 2001, **4**, 547; (f) G. A. Russell, P. Ngoviwatchai, H. L. Tashtoush, A. Pla-Dalmau and R. J. Khanna, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **110**, 3530; (g) A.-P. Schaffner, V. Darmency and P. Renaud, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2006, **45**, 5847.